

PRAGMATIC INTERPRETATION OF EPITHETS: EXPRESSIVENESS AND STYLISTIC EQUIVALENCE IN TRANSLATION (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE TRANSLATION OF THE NOVEL “BABUR THE TIGER”)

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the pragmatic interpretation of epithets and the strategies for achieving stylistic equivalence in the translation of Harold Lamb’s novel “Babur the Tiger” into Uzbek. Drawing on the theoretical foundations established by A.N. Veselovsky, I.R. Galperin, and I.V. Arnold, the research analyzes the semantic, structural, and evaluative functions of epithets as expressive devices. Special attention is given to how epithets shape the reader’s perception through emotional coloring, imagery, and cultural connotations. The study compares original epithetic constructions with their Uzbek renderings, identifying cases of semantic preservation, shifts in pragmatic meaning, amplification, and loss of irony. Through close comparative analysis, the article demonstrates that successful translation of epithets requires not only lexical equivalence but also careful consideration of culturally bound symbolism, stylistic nuance, and communicative intent. The findings highlight the translator’s role in maintaining expressiveness and ensuring pragmatically adequate and aesthetically coherent translations of literary imagery.

Epithet is one of the most widely used figurative means. A.N. Veselovsky, in his work published under the title “History of Poetics”, has a separate section entitled “From the History of Epithets”. In this section, the scientist defines an epithet as follows: “an epithet is a one-sided definition of a word, which renews or strengthens the meaning of a common noun, emphasizes some characteristic, remarkable quality of an object”¹. I.R. Galperin, who is highly engaged in English stylistics, gives A.N. Veselovsky’s definition in a complete form. According to him, “an epithet is an attributive word, phrase or even a sentence, used to describe an object and showing it to the reader, and often assigning to it some properties of the object, for the purpose of individual perception and assessment of these properties”². So, according to A.N. Veselovsky and I.R. Galperin, an epithet is formed by combining words of the noun class with words of the adjective class and serves to add to the original meaning of the noun to some extent. Another scientist who has done significant work in the stylistics of the English

¹ Веселовский А.Н. Историческая поэтика. – Ленинград: Художественная литература, 1940. – С. 73.

² Galperin I.R. Stylistics. – Moscow: “Higher School”, 1977. – P. 157.

language is I.V. Arnold. He also defined the epithet in the same sense as other scientists. It can be seen that there is a commonality in the opinions of scientists about the epithet.

Among the studies on epithets, the creation of “Epithet dictionaries”³ is of particular importance. In particular, A.L. Zelensky’s 214-page dictionary of epithets published in 1913 under the title “Epithets: Eternal Russian Writings” and K.S. Gorbachevich and E.P. Khablo’s 284-page “Dictionary of Epithets of the Russian Literary Language”⁴ published in Leningrad in 1979 are among them. These two dictionaries provide detailed information on what adjectives can be used to form epithets before words related to the noun class.

Information on the types of epithets is also given differently. A.N. Veselovsky divides them into two main types - tautological and explanatory epithets, and explanatory epithets are divided into two separate groups - metaphorical epithets and syncretic epithets⁵. A great contribution to the development of modern English stylistics I.V. Arnold, who added, also followed A.N. Veselovsky and analyzed the above types by taking examples from English sources⁶. I.R. Galperin perfectly divided epithets into types. They can be tabulated as follows.

2.4.2. Table

Epithet (I.R. Galperin “Stylistics”)							
Semantic		Structural					
Associated	Unassociated	Compositional				Distributive	
e.x: <i>dark forest</i>	e.x: <i>heart-burning smile</i>	Simple	Compound	Phrasal	Sentence	Systematic	Reversed

³ Зеленецкий А.Л. Эпитеты; Литературной русской речи. – Москва, 1913. – 214 с.

⁴ Горбачевич К.С., Хабло Е.П. Словарь эпитетов русского литературного языка. – Ленинград: «Наука», 1979. – 284 с.

⁵ Веселовский А.Н. Историческая поэтика. – Ленинград: Художественная литература, 1940. – С. 73-93.

⁶ Арнолд И.В. Стилистика. Современный английский язык. – Москва: «Наука», 2002. – С. 130-136.

		e.x: sweet perfume	e.x: true love	e.x: cloud-shapen giant	e.x: do-it-yourself attitude	e.x: wonderful, cruel, enchanted fatal, great city	e.x: sick chamber
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It is evident that I.R. Galperin has studied epithets perfectly. The one-sided approach of Western scholars in dividing artistic arts into types is clearly demonstrated by I.R. Galperin's approach to dividing epithets into types.

The presence of epithets in poetry and prose is very important, it serves to have a different effect on the reader's feelings, to a certain extent to strengthen them. Such lines are found in Abdulla Oripov.

*Qachondir Shimolning oppoq qoridan,
Seni yaratgandi zukko tabiat.
Ko'zingga rang berdi osmon qa'ridan,
Shul sabab moviydir bu ko'zlar behad.*⁷ (Abdulla Oripov)

Abdulla Oripov used the art of epithet in three places in the verses where he described colors. They are: 1) oppoq qor; 2) zukko tabiat; 3) moviy ko'zlar. If the poet had omitted the adjectives in these compounds, he would not have expressed the image and sign emotionally. Otherwise, the expressions would have been very poor. The adjective "oppoq" enhances the natural sign of the word "qor" and gives the meanings of purity, innocence, and beauty. It is better to use the art of animation together with the adjective "zukkolik" given to nature. The poet wanted to emphasize the presence of not only soul, but also cleverness in nature through this combination. The word "ko'zlar" was given an aesthetic-symbolic meaning through color (moviy). It is given as a symbol of beauty and tranquility in a single whole. All three epithets, according to I.R. Galperin's analysis, are structurally "connected" from a semantic point of view, and from a compositional point of view, they are simple epithets.

In the novel of "Babur the Tiger", epithets like the ones above are used in many places. Almost every sentence contains the participation of an epithet.

The first part of the novel describes the scene of the birth of Babur Mirzo. It contains the following sentence:

H.Lamb: *From **the ends of the valley** the chieftains of tribes and lords of the towns who owed allegiance to Omar Shaikh, rode in to felicitate the father on **the auspicious birth**, and to stuff themselves with **good eating**.* (H.L. 1961; 17)

⁷ Орипов А. Танланган асарлар, (Шерлар ва дostonлар). Иккинчи жилд. – Тошкент: Гофур Гулом номидаги Адабиёт ва санъат нашриёти, 2001. – Б. 19.

Word-by-word translation: *Vodiyning chekkalaridan Umarshayx mirzo egalik qiladigan shahar beklari va qabila sardorlari muvaffaqiyatli tug‘ulish bilan tabriklash hamda yaxshi ziyofatda qatnashi uchun yo‘lga otlangan edilar.. (Sh.I.)*

In fact, there are three places where the epithet is present. They are “the ends of the valley”, “auspicious birth” and “good eating”. The first “the ends of the valley” is considered an attributive phrase, poetically expressing geographical space. The event created the vastness of the area, the natural background. It evokes the impression of an epic, historical scene in the reader. In I.R.Galperin, epithets in such a structure are given in the “reversed” (changed) form. In English, such epithets are found in units that form possession through the preposition “of”⁸. The remaining two epithets are given in the form of adjective + noun. The phrase “the auspicious birth” is used to evaluate the event as positive and joyful. This phrase has a spiritual connection with holiness and joy. It creates a sense of joy, reverence, and a festive mood in the reader. The phrase “good eating” refers to a rich table, which in most cases can only be found in wealthy circles. The author seems to have introduced a subtle irony with this phrase. That is, after the description of the guests at the party, the nature of waste and greed for the party is often implied in such circles.

G.Sotimov: *Vodiyning chekka-chekkalaridan Umarshayx mirzo qo‘l ostida xizmatda bo‘lgan beklar, amirlar, mulk egalari va turli qavmlar sardorlari podshohni muborak sana – shahzodaning tug‘ilishi bilan tabriklash va buning sharafiga beriladigan to‘kin ziyofatda ishtirok etish uchun poytaxt sari yo‘lga otlandilar. (G‘S. 2015; 15)*

G. Sotimov translated the epithets identified in the original as follows:

- 1.“the ends of the valley” – “vodiyning chekka-chekkalaridan”;
- 2.“the auspicious birth” – “muborak sana – shahzodaning tugilishi”;
- 3.“good eating” – “to‘kin ziyofat”.

The original epithet “the ends of the valley” was preserved in its full meaning in the translation. In particular, the repeated use of the word “chekka” performed an amplifying function, and the translator thereby wanted to convey the breadth and size of the geographical space in the original. Through this approach, pragmatics was preserved in the translation. The positive-evaluative meaning of the original “auspicious” quality is fully conveyed in the Uzbek translation through the word “muborak”. The word “birth” is given by the somewhat abstract word “sana”. The fact that the translator expresses it as “muborak sana-shahzoding tug‘ilishi” shows that he translated it by adding additional information to the original. After all, translating the phrase “the auspicious birth” literally as simply “omadli tog‘ilish” would have made the pragmatic meaning even more ambiguous for the reader. The translator noticed this and, by adding additions, saved the reader from this ambiguity. The ironic tone in the English expression took on a formal and neutral tone in the translation. “A sumptuous feast” is used in an artistic, but positive sense. As a result, pragmatics is lost, but cultural coherence is ensured.

Bibliography:

1.Galperin I.R. Stylistics. – Moscow: “Higher School”, 1977. – 344 p.

⁸ Galperin I.R. Stylistics. – Moscow: “Higher School”, 1977. p. 160.

- 2.Орипов А. Танланган асарлар, (Шерлар ва дostonлар). Иккинчи жилд. – Тошкент: Гофур Гулом номидаги Адабиёт ва санъат нашриёти, 2001. – 220 б.
- 3.Веселовский А.Н. Историческая поэтика. – Ленинград: Художественная литература, 1940. – 432 с.
- 4.Арнольд И.В. Стилистика. Современный английский язык: Учебник для вузов. – 5-е изд., испр. и доп. – Москва: Флинта: Наука, 2002. – 384 с.
- 5.Горбачевич К.С., Хабло Е.П. Словарь эпитетов вусского литературного языка. – Ленинград: «Наука», 1979. – 284 с.
- 6.Зеленецкий А.Л. Эпитеты; Литературной русской рѣчи. – Москва, 1913. – 214 с.

